

ANALYSIS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF CODE POTENTIAL AND DEPENDENCE ON ASSESSMENT METHODS

Ziyoda Begmatova

Head of Human Resources Department, Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi

z.begmatovatatu@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This article examines the practical tasks, factors, and economic success of effective personnel management, as well as the need to analyze personnel potential and apply applicable methods. It is designed to realize work potential, develop personal abilities, provide people with satisfaction from work done and public recognition of their achievements, and provide a comfortable environment. Personnel planning is also aimed at meeting the needs of production and ensuring the interests of employees and society as a whole. Today, more than ever, it is necessary to look for opportunities to harmonize market conditions and the interests of the company's employee.*

Keywords: *personnel potential, human resources, socio-psychological qualities, socio-demographic, expert analysis and empirical.*

The need to analyze personnel potential and use methods.

In order to effectively use the human resources of the enterprise, it is important to analyze it in all respects. The expediency of the analysis of personnel potential is manifested, as a rule, at the stage of development of plans, changes in activities, new innovative projects, decision-making related to the structure of enterprises themselves, recruitment, action planning and evaluation.

Certification

It should be noted that the analysis of personnel potential should be carried out regularly. This work should be carried out by employees of the personnel department or personnel management services. In the analysis of personnel potential, since it concerns people, who are the main resource of any enterprise, first of all, it is necessary to study the economic and socio-psychological factor (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Socio-psychological factors in the analysis of personnel potential.

In order to solve problems in determining the sources and directions of satisfaction with the human resources of the enterprise, it is necessary to base the criteria on the suitability of employees for a certain job or position. The need to analyze the personnel potential of the

enterprise is to determine the level of staffing necessary to fulfill the current and future tasks of the enterprise. Therefore, the relevance of methods of analyzing the personnel potential of the enterprise is increasing. In this regard, human resources can be defined as the total number of employees, including the capabilities of employees who are used in production and those who are not involved. Personnel potential should be analyzed statically and dynamically.

In terms of the level achieved so far and taking into account its development and improvement in the future, the personnel potential should be considered as the general level of staffing of the enterprise's ability to exist and develop.

Staffing capacity includes:

- components of human resources;
- personal and business characteristics;
- socio-psychological qualities;
- labor potential;
- the formal structure of the team;

The components of human resources are:

- Labor capacity;
- The official structure of the team;
- Informal structure of the team;
- Personal and business characteristics;
- Social and psychological qualities;
- Organizational and management factors;
- Macrostructural factors.

All of the above factors, to varying degrees, determine the work behavior of the employee and affect the potential of personnel.

The main variables of personnel potential analysis:

- age;
- physical health status of employees;
- qualification, quality of personnel training;
- proper selection and placement of personnel;
- experience and qualifications of workers and employees;
- workforce compatibility;
- moral and psychological climate in the team;
- job satisfaction;
- social protection of workers.

In order to conduct an in-depth and comprehensive analysis of personnel potential, first of all, it is necessary to have an idea of the quality of the company's employees. Because the level of quality composition of employees determines the efficiency of the enterprise. Therefore, before starting the analysis of personnel potential, work should be carried out to determine the quality of the company's employees. The quality of the decisions made and the results of their implementation largely depend on the personal characteristics of employees, their general educational qualifications and professional qualifications.

There are also several types of conflicts in the company's satisfaction with human resources (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Types of disputes.

The analysis of the quality composition of employees should begin with the study of socio-demographic data - gender, age, education, work experience, qualifications, etc. The optimal staffing level of managers and specialists largely determines the efficiency of a certain economic system, because the quality of the decisions made and the results of their implementation depend on the personal qualities of these employees, their level of general education and skills.

The analysis of the quality composition of employees includes the study of employees by gender, age, education, qualifications, work experience and other socio-demographic aspects. One of the main factors of the quality composition of employees is the correct ratio of the number of men and women in various positions and professional groups.

Currently, the general trends in the use of men and women in positions are:

- network managers for men (directors of enterprises, heads of workshops, sections, shifts);
- and women work better in the positions of functional managers (heads of departments, bureaus, sectors, groups) and specialists.

Analysis of the quality composition of employees based on their education and qualifications determines the quantitative composition of highly educated employees, the quality level of placement of employees in positions, the level of optimal use of highly educated specialists, etc. The assessment of the quality of placement of employees is calculated as the coefficient of division of the number of highly educated specialists occupying managerial and engineering positions by the total number of positions requiring replacement by specialists.

In the analysis of the quality structure of the management staff, it is important to determine the quality indicators of personnel placement by specialty and the level of acceptability of their use, which helps to improve the quality of personnel work planning and to identify additional needs.

For specialists and the basis for development and implementation, 32 is the basis for the improvement of professional and qualified content and the placement of management personnel. Timely analysis of the dynamics reflecting the quality composition, location and use of specialists is a successful organization of work with personnel.

The quality composition of management personnel should be studied based on the analysis of their tenure and career growth.

- good organization of work on the orientation and professional selection of employees, the study of their personal and business qualities based on a scientifically based assessment of their abilities and work results;

- organization of professional training of management personnel as a reserve for promotion, regular improvement of business skills and educational level of each employee;
- organization of qualified placement of personnel based on the use of modern forms and methods of working with personnel (conducting selections for projects and attestation for positions, studying public opinion, organizing professional promotion, procedures for motivating employees increase efficiency, etc.);
- taking into account the specific characteristics of different categories of workers (young professionals, masters, substitute groups, etc.), raising the level of educational and ideological work with personnel based on the competent organization of their production and social adaptation.

In recent years, systematic analysis methods (decomposition method and sequential replacement method, comparison method and objective systematization method), expert analysis method and the main 33 components, experimental method and collective notebook method have been widely used in the study of human resources. .

A systematic approach based on systematic analysis is of great importance in personnel management. Applying a systematic approach to personnel management involves studying the entire management system as a whole and studying its components: functions, goals, organizational structure of personnel, technical management tools, main categories and methods of personnel. their management, information, management technology, management decisions, identifying different types of communication between these components and the external environment and bringing them into a unified picture.

The personnel management system should be divided into subsystems, subsystems into functions, and functions into procedures. In this case, after the procedure - into operations, from operations - into elements, and each part to be checked is modeled and synthesized.

A competency system is used to analyze the potential of an employee. For example, to study the effect of each component on the performance of employees, it is necessary to try to exclude the influence of other factors using the method of sequential replacement. This method makes it possible to separately study the impact of each factor on the formation of the personnel management system, excluding the influence of other factors. The factors are ranked and the most important ones are selected. Systematic analysis does not exclude the comparative method.

Comparison method allows to compare the company's current personnel management system with another similar system of an advanced company or a standard situation formed on the basis of the positive experience of other organizations and enterprises. The use of this method, for example, the analysis of personnel management, taking into account the time factor, makes it possible to compare the desired state of this subsystem in the future with the normative state or its state in the past period. This ultimately eliminates inconsistencies and increases comparability. The use of the goal systematization method is an important and necessary condition of system analysis. With its help, it is possible to ensure the quantitative and qualitative justification of the objectives of the personnel management subsystem in accordance with the goals of the organization. Using this method, you can analyze the goals, sort them and place them in the system. This method allows to ensure correlation and comparison of goals of different levels of personnel management.

Expert analysis as for the analysis of personnel potential using the method, it is necessary to involve highly qualified specialists in the field of personnel management, management personnel in the improvement process. The main thing in using this method is to develop forms of

systematization, recording and clear presentation of experts' opinions and conclusions. The method of expert analysis reveals the main directions of improvement of personnel management, evaluation of analysis results and causes of deficiencies. The method of principal components is closely related to systematic analysis, and this method allows to reflect the characteristics of many other indicators describing a certain phenomenon in one indicator (principal component).

Empirical the use of the method is related to systematic and situational analysis. This method is based on previous experience with a particular or similar management system. Using the replacement method, important elements of operations are selected, and the rest are sorted according to the level of importance. Similar operations, procedures, functions are selected in the reverse order, effective subsystems are formed, and as a result, the personnel management system is formed.

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